

Church of St. John, Trachiniakos

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Entry tags: Crete, Religious Group, Byzantine, Church, Byzantine, Religious Place, Medieval Christianity, Monument, Orthodoxy

The church of St. John in the village of Trachiniakos (just west of Kandanos in the southwest corner of Crete) is a single nave construction with a barrel-vaulted interior and a saddle roof exterior. Dated by a partially preserved dedicatory inscription to 1328-29, the church is located on the left side of a narrow road leading to the vibrant olive groves surrounding the village. The church is divided into two bays by a transverse arch with two niches along both the north and south walls. A modern wooden iconostasis divides the sanctuary from the nave. Richly decorated and well preserved, the wall paintings have been ascribed to the work of two painters, one in the style of the Cretan painter Ioannis Pagomenos. The half dome of the sanctuary includes the image of the Virgin Platytera above the image of two co-officiating bishops, St. Basil and St. John Chrysostom. The triumphal arch includes the image of the Hospitality of Abraham above the Annunciation. Below both the Angel Gabriel and the virgin are the deacon saints St. Stephen and St. Romanus the Melodist. Bishop saints, including the image of Leo of Catania, line both the northern and southern walls of the sanctuary. In the nave, the barrel vault is decorated with scenes from the Christological cycle including images of the Baptism of Christ, the Raising of Lazarus and the Helkomenos. The archway, decorated with the prophets David, Daniel, Solomon and Isaiah, is set out from the barrel vault and divides the eastern and western niches on either side. The titular saint, St. John the Evangelist, is painted in the eastern niche along the northern wall. Facing towards the altar holding a book, he is framed by a decorative archway. Above him, two medallions bearing representations of a young saint and an angel are likely connected to the symbology of the saint. The western niche on the northern wall includes three military saints, St. Theodore, St. George and St. Dimitrios, all on horseback below the blessing hands of the Archangel Raphael. All three spear dragons at the bottom of the scene. To the west of the niche is the image of the monastic saint St. Onouphrius and next to him the image of St. John the Hermit. Likewise, the eastern niche on the southern wall holds a large image of the Archangel Michael wings outstretched. He is flanked to his left by St. Mamas. Above them, three medallions with red and green backgrounds hold the images of an eagle, a lion and an ox representing the three symbols of the evangelists, an unusual addition to Cretan churches of this period. The western niche includes the large image of Saints Constantine and Helena flanked by St. Procopius. They are blessed from above by St. Sophia. Between the eastern and western niche is the image of St. Nikitas portrayed in military garb. West of the niche are the images of two female saints: St. Kyriaki and St. Paraskevi. The western wall, albeit damaged, includes the image of the Crucifixion above the dedicatory inscription. The dedicatory inscription states that the church was built in the year 6837 (1328-29) at the expense of three families from the village. The doorway is flanked by four female saints, St. Barbara and St. Marina on the left and two unnamed female saints on the right.

Date Range: 1329 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Trachiniakos, Selino, Crete

Region tags: Greece, Crete

The village of Trachiniakos is outside the village of Kandanos in the province of Selino (Chania) in the southwest corner of Crete.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Tree, grove, or forest

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

- Yes

↳ A single structure

- Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

- Other [specify]: Single nave chapel with a barrel vault interior and a saddle roof exterior

↳ One single feature

- Clearing

↳ A group of structures:

- No

↳ A group of features:

- No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

- No

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

- Worship

↳ Worship:

- Other [specify]: Both communal and individual

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

- Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Dedicated to St. John

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– No

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Spatharakis, Ioannis. Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. See no. 25, 76 (with earlier bibliography)
- Source 2: Bissinger, Manfred. Kreta. Byzantinische Wandmalerei. Münchener Arbeiten Zur Kunstgeschichte Und Archäologie 4. Munich: Editio Maris, 1995. See 99 no. 57
- Source 3: Gerola, Giuseppe, and K. Lassithiotakis. Τοπογραφικός κατάλογος των τοιχογραφημένων εκκλησιών της Κρήτης. Edited by K. Lassithiotakis. Heraklion: Εταιρίας Κρητικών Ιστορικών Μελετών, 1961. See no. 154

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature
– Clearing

– Trackway or road-surface

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– I don't know

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Other [specify]: The dedicatory inscription states that the church was built at the expense of three families from the village.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Sources and Excavations

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- Source 1: Spatharakis, Ioannis. *Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete*. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. See no. 25, 76 (with earlier bibliography)
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Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

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A single structure

– Yes

The structure has a definite shape

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Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
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↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
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↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

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Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: There is a modern wooden iconostasis separating the sanctuary

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The wall paintings contain images of Christ in the Christological cycle.

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The wall paintings include standing figures of saints, monks and prophets.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood
– I don't know

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Plaster, stone

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

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Decoration

Is decoration present:

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↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

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↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

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↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

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↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

Portrayals of afterlife

– No

Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Humans

– No

Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Human narratives

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is divination present:

– No

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– No

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:
– I don't know

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:
– No

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:
– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:
– No

Are festivals present:
– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:
– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:
– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with

subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service

Religious Specialists

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Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

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Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The local Archaeological Service

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Church of St. John, Trachiniakos, Spatharakis, Ioannis. Dated Byzantine Wall Paintings of Crete. Leiden: Alexandros Press, 2001. p.76 (no. 25)

Reference: Church of St. John, Trachiniakos, Bissinger, Manfred. Kreta. Byzantinische Wandmalerei. Münchener Arbeiten Zur Kunstgeschichte Und Archäologie 4. Munich: Editio Maris, 1995. p.99 (no. 57)

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Reference: Church of St. John, Trachiniakos, Sucrow, Alexandra. "Die Wandmalereien Des Ioannes Pagomenos in Kirchen Der Ersten Hälfte Des 14. Jahrhunderts Auf Kreta". Friedrich-Wilhelms-Universität, Bonn, 1994. p.145-46